

REVIEW OF APPROACHES AND TECHNOLOGIES OF ADAPTIVE LEARNING SYSTEMS FOR LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract. *This article reviews various approaches and technologies of adaptive learning systems used for learning English. Adaptive learning allows for the individualization of the learning process, taking into account the knowledge level, abilities, and interests of each learner. The article analyzes the methods of collecting and analyzing data in adaptive systems, as well as the role of such modern technologies as artificial intelligence and machine learning.*

Keywords: *adaptive learning, English language, artificial intelligence, machine learning, data analysis, personalized learning.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada ingliz tilini o'rganishda adaptiv o'quv tizimlarining turli usullari va texnologiyalari tahlil qilinadi. Adaptiv o'quv tizimi har bir talabaning bilim darajasi, qobiliyatlari va qiziqishlariga mos ravishda o'quv jarayonini individuallashtirishga imkon beradi. Maqolada adaptiv o'quv tizimlarida qo'llaniladigan turli xil ma'lumotlarni to'plash va tahlil qilish usullari, shuningdek, sun'iy intellekt va mashinaviy o'rganish kabi zamonaviy texnologiyalarning roli ko'rib chiqiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *adaptiv o'quv, ingliz tili, sun'iy intellekt, mashinaviy o'rganish, ma'lumotlar tahlili, individuallashtirilgan o'quv.*

Introduction

Adaptive learning is an individual approach to learning, in which the learning process automatically adjusts to the unique needs and pace of each student. In the context of learning English, adaptive systems allow you to create personalized training programs, taking into account the level of language proficiency, strengths and weaknesses of the student, their learning goals and preferences.

Adaptive learning is based on cognitive psychology and learning theory, for example:

Student Modeling. Create an individual student model that reflects their knowledge, skills, and preferences.

Data Analysis. Collecting and analyzing data about the learning process to adapt the learning material.

Intelligent algorithms. Using machine learning algorithms to make decisions about the choice of educational materials and tasks.

The basis of any adaptive learning system is data analysis. By collecting and processing information about the learning process, the system can accurately determine the current level of knowledge of the student, his strengths and weaknesses, as well as his preferences in learning. This allows you to create individual learning paths and ensure maximum learning efficiency by collecting: demographic data (age, gender, education level, native language, etc.), comparative knowledge (input test results, language proficiency level), behavioral data (time spent completing tasks, number of attempts, errors, selection of additional materials), interaction with the interface (frequency of using various system functions, response time to tasks), physiological data (data on brain activity when using special devices). When analyzing data, you can see how: the system automatically selects tasks that correspond to the student's level of knowledge,

individual comments on the student's mistakes, additional materials for self-study, and automatic adjustment of the learning rate depending on the student's progress.

Materials and methods

There are several approaches to adaptive learning:

Content adaptation - changing the content of educational materials depending on the student's level; Process adaptation - changing the order and pace of material submission; Interface adaptation - changing the appearance and functionality of the learning platform.

Technologies in adaptive systems, like artificial intelligence, are used to create intelligent tutors and analyze big data. Machine learning allows systems to "learn" from data collected about each student. Machine learning algorithms can identify patterns in students' behavior, predict their academic performance, and adapt the learning process. Neural networks both mimic the work of the human brain and are able to process large amounts of data, revealing complex relationships between various variables. Natural language Processing (NLP) allows systems to understand and generate human language. Databases store information about each student, their progress and preferences. Cloud technologies provide access to data and applications from any device connected to the Internet. Gamification uses game elements to increase students' motivation and engagement. Virtual and augmented reality create immersive learning environments. The blockchain ensures the security and transparency of student achievement data.

Results and discussion

Studies show that adaptive learning systems significantly increase the effectiveness of learning compared to traditional methods. This is due to the fact that they allow you to take into account the individual characteristics of students, such as the level of knowledge, the rate of assimilation of material, interests and preferences, which contributes to a more personalized approach. For example, if a student shows poor results in grammar, the system may offer additional exercises to eliminate weaknesses. Adaptive systems offer the user immediate feedback on completed tasks, which allows the student to quickly correct mistakes and strengthen their knowledge. Technologies such as Duolingo and Lingvist, use the method of interval repetition to optimize the process of memorizing vocabulary and grammatical structures. This increases the long-term memorability of the material and accelerates the process of assimilation.

Lingvist is a state-of-the-art online platform for learning foreign languages, including English, that uses machine learning and data analytics to create personalized learning trajectories. It selects content based on an analysis of what the student has already learned and how quickly they have learned it. This allows you to avoid repeating familiar topics and focus on new and complex ones. It uses machine learning algorithms to evaluate which words or expressions the student has learned and which ones they need to repeat. Provides students with real-time feedback on the correct completion of tasks and adjusts the choice of exercises.

Conclusion

Adaptive systems open up new opportunities for personalizing English language learning. They make it possible to increase the effectiveness of learning, increase the motivation of students and make the learning process more interesting. The use of technology in adaptive systems increases the effectiveness of learning, as tasks and materials are selected individually for each student, which allows you to speed up the learning process and improve results;

increasing motivation, a personalized approach makes learning more interesting and exciting. Automating routine tasks allows the teacher to focus on the more creative aspects of learning.

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